

Enzyme mediated hydrolysis of organic fraction of municipal solid waste (OFMSW) : A short review

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Abstract : One of the major advancements in the field of municipal solid waste management (MSWM) techniques is the introduction of enzymatic hydrolysis in the anaerobic digestion (AD) process. The hydrolysis step in AD has always been rate-limiting irrespective of the nature of the waste stabilized. It has been observed from several past studies that application of various enzymes during the AD of complex substrates, present in the generated solid organic waste leads to a substantial enhancement of the rate-limiting hydrolytic phase. The present review gives a brief insight on the different aspects of enzymatic hydrolysis such as, its scope, the factors affecting its rate, pre-treatment techniques involved prior to its application, and its brief mechanism. Not only that, a detailed description about the various biological, physical and chemical parameters influencing the enzymatic hydrolysis of lignocellulosic biomass has been given. In addition, various past experiences of enzymatic hydrolysis have been discussed at length. Lastly, the future scope of enzymatic hydrolysis in the field of AD, pertaining to stabilization of solid organic waste, has been also discussed.

Keywords : Enzymatic hydrolysis, anaerobic digestion, OFMSW, pre-treatment, lignocellulose, enzyme.

I. Introduction

Day-by-day the rate of global municipal solid waste (MSW) generation is increasing at an alarming rate. Under this circumstance, the municipalities across the world should look forward to adopting a technoeconomically viable and environment-friendly strategy for stabilizing the municipal solid wastes. In this regard, anaerobic digestion (AD) has developed by leaps and bounds since its inception in the early 20th century¹. The process of AD helps in striking a more than desirable balance between the generation and stabilization rates of MSW besides significantly contributing to the renewable energy sector. Under anaerobic conditions, the organic fraction of municipal solid waste (OFMSW) degrades in three steps namely, hydrolysis, acidogenesis, and methanogenesis. Fig. 1 (adopted from Ref. 2) shows the biochemical pathway of AD of OFMSW. The first and foremost step i.e. hydrolysis, involves transforming

higher molecular-mass compounds into simpler compounds which are suitable for use as a source of energy and cell tissue. Therefore, hydrolysis can be defined as the conversion of organic polymers and lipids into basic structural building blocks such as fatty acids, monosaccharides, amino acids, and similar compounds.

On certain occasions involving the degradation of complex biodegradable substrates, the process of hydrolysis is mediated by the help of extra-cellular enzymes. This is defined as enzyme mediated hydrolysis. Following the conversion into simpler monomers, further breakdown of the products occur into simple organic acids, alcohols and long chain fatty acids via acidogenesis. During the third phase i.e. methanogenesis, conversion of the products of acidogenesis into gaseous end products, like sulfur dioxide, carbon dioxide and methane, occur. Past researches have adequately revealed that hydrolysis is

Fig. 1. Biochemical pathway of AD of OFMSW (Adopted from Ref. 2).

the rate limiting phase in AD. This can be due to the fact that complex organic substrates tend to form toxic by-products (complex heterocyclic compounds) or non-desirable volatile fatty acids (VFAs) during hydrolysis²⁸, which in turn inhibit the remainder of the AD process³. It can be thus said that if the rate of hydrolysis is enhanced, the rate of AD would be significantly improved. As such, many researches based on different pre-treatment methods have been conducted to accelerate the hydrolysis phase with an aim to obtain suitable by-product⁴.

Studies have revealed that MSW mostly comprises of organic matter (60–70%), of which the fraction of food waste (FW) and fruit and vegetable waste (FVW) constitutes a major part¹⁰¹. Of the generated FW and FVW a major part is comprised of lignocellulosic matter. Lignocellulosic matter is made of cellulose (38–50%), hemicelluloses (23–32%), lignin (15–25%), and small amounts of extractives^{5,6}. For this reason hydrolysis of the lignocellulosic material is considered a significantly important step in the overall AD process. The major problem associated

with this hydrolysis step is the saccharification of the lignocelluloses, which are insoluble and crystalline. Since the reaction rate of the cellulosic matter present in the lignocelluloses, undergoing hydrolysis, depends on the available surface area, their insoluble and crystalline structures necessitate greatest degree of solubilization. Many lignocellulosic wastes containing higher percentages of lignin do not chemically inhibit cellulose solubilization, but may limit access of the enzymes to the cellulose⁷.

Researchers over the past years have mainly focused on the ability and the various limitations of different microbial enzyme systems to completely hydrolyze the plant cell walls, which are considered as the structural polysaccharides. With the identification and characterization of these extracellular microbial enzymatic systems, studies concerning the differences and clear similarities have been initiated⁸. The aim of the present review is to ascertain the scope of enhancing the hydrolysis step in AD of OFMSW, by addition of enzymes. The various factors that affect the scope of enzymatic hydrolysis have been discussed critically. In addition, the major breakthroughs pertaining to the lab-scale and pilot-scale studies, on enzymatic hydrolysis, conducted hitherto have been highlighted. These apart, the future scopes concerning the different areas of enzymatic hydrolysis which are not explored yet, have been also discussed.

II. Scope of hydrolysis in AD of OFMSW

The composition of OFMSW varies greatly with different regions and climate. It has been observed that in certain agriculturally dependent regions the percentage of cellulose and lignocellulose in OFMSW are alarmingly high. In this regard, the principal factors which are responsible for influencing the enzymatic hydrolysis of cellulose and lignocellulose have to be understood properly. The steps which lead to the enzymatic hydrolysis of cellulose^{9,10} include : (1) enzyme transfer from bulk aqueous phase to surface of the cellulose particles, (2) adsorption of those

enzymes followed by the formation of enzyme-substrate complexes (ES), (3) hydrolysis of cellulose, (4) transfer of glucose, cellodextrins and cellobiose to the bulk aqueous phase from the surface of cellulose particles, and (5) hydrolysis of the transferred cellobiose and cellodextrins into glucose, in the aqueous phase. According to many researchers, the most complicated steps from the above are the adsorption of enzymes and the formation of ES¹¹⁻¹³. The structural features of cellulose, the interaction modality between the cellulase and the cellulose fiber, the nature of the cellulases employed, and the susceptibility of the employed enzymes to product inhibition can be considered as the influential factors during the enzymatic hydrolysis^{14,15}.

Generally hydrolysis is regarded as the rate limiting step in AD of OFMSW; however, during AD of highly biodegradable substrates such as, carbohydrate, protein and fats, acidogenesis becomes the rate limiting step^{16,17}. Previous studies have shown that the typical FVW is poor in cellulose. However, nature of FVW varies largely depending upon the climatological conditions and the prevailing food habits of the inhabitants in an area. Hydrolysis has a pivotal role in acidogenesis and methanogenesis phases. If rate of hydrolysis is too low the subsequent phases are delayed greatly and this affects the cost aspect of the overall AD process. If hydrolysis rate is high, the organic acid and alcohol production rate becomes high and the pH of the AD system decreases. As a consequence of this shock loading, disruptions of microbial cells occur and the overall stability of the AD process gets affected. It can be clearly said that hydrolysis phase has a huge impact on the subsequent acidogenesis and methanogenesis phases, and in order to improve the overall efficiency of the AD process the hydrolysis step must be optimized.

III. Scope of enzymatic hydrolysis

The scope of enzymatic hydrolysis is depended on the nature of the lignocellulosic substrate under-

going hydrolysis and, the type of enzymes that carry out the hydrolysis. In addition, other relevant factors such as, pre-treatment technique adopted and overall cost aspect, also become equally vital during the enzymatic application in AD of OFMSW. Broadly, the scope of enzymatic hydrolysis can be directly linked with the limitations surrounding enzymatic hydrolysis and the principle involved in improving the rate of hydrolysis via application of enzymes.

C1. Limitations of enzymatic hydrolysis

Various enzyme-related and substrate-related factors contribute to the enzymatic hydrolysis of lignocellulosic substrate. The selection of a particular type of pre-treatment technique is largely based on the composition of the liquid fraction and solid process streams. In order to improve the degree of enzymatic saccharification, reduction in the degree of certain pre-treatment techniques may be necessitated sometimes for lowering the overall monetary cost. However, optimizing the degree of pre-treatment is extremely vital since lower degree of pre-treatment may result in the release of less sugar. It may necessitate the need for applying higher amounts of different enzyme types for achieving the targeted sugar yields from both cellulose and hemicellulose fractions. Thus it is essential to develop hemicellulases along with other enzyme types, which would be capable of completely degrading lignocellulosic components. Recent studies have focused on developing such newly cultured balanced enzymatic complexes which are capable of modifying the complex structures of lignocellulosic materials^{18,19}.

C2. Principle of improving the rate of hydrolysis via application of enzyme

Enzymatic hydrolysis has several advantages over conventional hydrolysis. The enzymes hydrolyzing cellulose are very specific and do not produce undesirable by-products. Enzymatic pre-treatment thus promotes the hydrolysis of lignocellulosic matter, breaking it down to lower molecular weight substances that can be readily utilized by the microbes.

For instance, the recalcitrance to enzymes exhibited by the raw lignocellulosic material has prompted researchers to come up with a suitable pre-treatment technique that has been found to facilitate access of enzymes to plant polysaccharides. As such, a good and affordable pretreatment technique is an essential prerequisite to improve the enzymatic hydrolysis of lignocellulosic materials, whose complex structures make it extremely challenging for only the enzymes to carry out the hydrolysis. The past decades have thus witnessed various pre-treatment strategies with a view to improve the digestibility of lignocellulosic materials at affordable rates²⁰.

IV. Substrate- and enzyme-related factors affecting enzymatic hydrolysis

Researchers, over the years, have focused on the techniques to achieve complete hydrolysis of the structural polysaccharides of plant cells using different microbial systems. However, the discovery of a single mechanism capable of carrying out total lignocellulosic saccharification has not been done yet. This is largely due to the heterogeneous nature of the supramolecular structure that has been naturally prevalent in lignocellulosic matrices. The heterogeneous structure makes it difficult to understand the enzyme-complex and substrate interaction, even though it has become clear that the efficiency of enzymatic complex is related to the inherent structural characteristics of the substrates and/or the changes occurring with saccharification proceeds⁸. Enzymatic hydrolysis of lignocellulosic materials can thus be influenced by both enzyme efficiency and the inherent character (physicochemical and morphological) of the lignocellulosic material. As mentioned earlier, the enzymatic hydrolysis of lignocellulosic materials depends on two major factors : enzyme related factors and, substrate related factors²⁰.

The substrate related factors are as follows :

D1. Degree of polymerization

Crystallinity, which is one of the structural characteristics of a substrate, is largely influenced by the

degree of polymerization. Hydrolysis or depolymerization of cellulose is believed to be affected by the role of glucan chain length²¹. Enzymatic hydrolysis of endoglucanases cut at the internal sites of the less ordered cellulose chains thereby increasing the degree of depolymerization of the cellulosic substrates. The increased recalcitrance due to the presence of residual crystalline cellulose has been one of the major issues effecting the depolymerization of celluloses regardless of whether the cellulose has been levelled-off or not⁸. In this regard, different pretreatments on cellulose chain length have increased the degree of depolymerization in solids. The effect of pretreatment has been found to be especially prominent in the removal of xylan, with a more severe impact in the reduction of cellulose chain than lignin chain²².

D2. Cellulose crystallinity

Even though the rate of hydrolysis of relatively refined substrates has been influenced by the degree of polymerization and cellulose crystallinity²³, different studies have revealed that the aforesaid factors solely do not explain the importance of recalcitrance in lignocelluloses²¹. The studies based on mechanically pre-treated refined cellulosic substrate have found a positive correlation between hydrolysis and cellulosic crystallinity. This has been due to the apparent change in the crystallinity indices of the cellulosic substrate. Other similar pretreatment strategies which are responsible to decrease crystallinity, resulting in the increase of specific surface area, have also been explored hitherto. The increase in specific surface area has been one of the major reasons to enhance the degree of hydrolysis^{24,25}. Studies concerning hydrolysis of naturally occurring lignocellulosic substrates have been helpful in understanding the effect that crystallinity has on hindering the hydrolysis reaction. This is especially crucial given the fact that most studies have failed to explain the relation between the rates of hydrolysis reactions and crystallinity. Even though hydrolysability was improved through pre-treatment of the lignocellulosic

matter but in some instances the improved hydrolysability accounted for increased crystallinity index of the pretreated cellulose fraction. This has been mostly due to the removal of the amorphous cellulose via various pre-treatments, e.g. steam explosion⁸. In contrast, alkaline pre-treatments have shown to cause less effect, and even reduced biomass crystallinity in some cases²².

D3. Lignin barrier (content and distribution)

Cellulose consists of lignin and hemicellulosic matter which are mainly responsible for reducing the entry of cellulase into the cellulosic substrate, thereby impeding the hydrolysis rate⁸. Lignin acts as a physical barrier and prevents the digestible fractions of cellulose from getting hydrolyzed²³. In addition, lignin renders to the non-productivity of the added enzymes by binding itself to the added cellulolytic enzymes²⁶. Numerous strategies, such as alkali extraction and addition of protein or other additives (e.g. polyethylene glycol and Tween)²⁷, have been studied recently with the view to overcome the non-productive adsorption of cellulolytic enzymes to lignin. These strategies have to be reviewed judiciously since the use of additives results in the additional cost of ethanol production and other benefits availed with regards to the enhancement of the hydrolysis step.

D4. Hemicellulose content

Studies have revealed that the degree of cellulose hydrolysis gets significantly enhanced with the removal of hemicellulose from the cellulose fraction. This is because with the removal of the hemicellulose fraction the mean pore size of the cellulose increases, resulting in the better accessibility of enzymes to cellulose. The recovery of hemicellulosic sugar from pre-treated organic solids, for the purpose of fermentable sugar production, has been of significant interest in recent times. This has led to the requirement of hemicellulosic modification²⁹. In this regard, the acetylation of hemicellulose is one of the major factors since lignin and acetyl groups

are attached to hemicellulose matrix, which are major hindering factors in the breakdown of polysaccharides²³.

D5. Feedstock particle size and surface area

The accessibility of substrate to cellulolytic enzymes can be regarded as one of the most important factors influencing the degree of the hydrolysis process. It has been observed from past studies that substrate particle size reduction leads to increase in the specific surface area and subsequent accessibility of enzymes to substrate³⁰. Therefore, any pretreatment technique which increases the specific surface area available is desirable in order to enhance the process of enzymatic hydrolysis.

D6. Porosity

Past studies have showed that substrate pore size with respect to size of the enzymes has been one of the decisive factors in limiting the rate of hydrolysis especially in case of lignocellulosic biomass²⁸. This can be attributed to the fact that enzyme particles tend to get trapped in the external pores of the lignocellulosic materials, which tend to be smaller than the internal pores³¹. In order to overcome this, various pretreatments can be adopted which in essence would improve the hydrolysis rate.

The enzyme related factors are as follows :

D7. Synergism

Synergism can be defined as the combined action of two or more enzymes together, which is usually greater than the sum of their individual actions. The absence of synergism is an important factor limiting the hydrolysis process in case of microcrystalline cellulose³². For instance, during the enzymatic hydrolysis of Avicel³³ a gradual decrease in the specific activity of the adsorbed enzyme was noticed. Given the relation between cellulose structural characteristics and synergism, during enzymatic hydrolysis of ideal substrates, questions came up regarding the role between synergism and hydrolysis in case of more structurally heterogeneous lignocellulosic sub-

strates. These is not found out yet and needs to be delved into⁸.

D8. Adsorption

The primary difference between enzymatic hydrolysis and other enzymatic reactions is that in case of the later the substrate remains largely insoluble and necessitates the adsorption of enzyme before undergoing hydrolysis. Substrate, such as lignocellulose, requires enzymatic interaction via adsorption before it can undergo hydrolysis. It has been observed that the interaction between the adsorbate, cellulase, and the adsorbent, lignocellulose is facilitated by a cellulose-binding domain (CBD), in addition to the catalytic domain. Similar mode of enzyme-substrate interaction has also been observed in case of other polysaccharide-degrading enzymes too.

V. Physical, chemical and biological factors affecting enzymatic hydrolysis

The enzymatic hydrolysis of lignocellulosic biomass present in OFMSW gets accelerated if preceded by biological pretreatments³⁴. These biological pretreatments, which alter the physiochemical structure of lignocellulosic biomass, are dependent on several physical, chemical, and biological factors such as pH, temperature, moisture content, contact/incubation period, particle size, structural quality of lignocellulosic biomass, polysaccharide loss, co-culture of microbes, and microbial adaptation. Optimization of these aforesaid factors is thus crucial towards enhancing the rate of lignocellulosic biomass degradation.

E1. pH

Enzymatic hydrolysis of lignocellulosic biomass decreases system pH following a certain period of microbial activity. Various studies in the past have corroborated this fact. In a system targeted to assess the influence of initial pH on organic acids formation, which is very common during hydrolysis of complex lignocellulosic biomass, by *Acinetobacter* sp.³⁵, it was observed that the medium pH sharply

dropped from 7.0 to less than 4.0 within 10 days of incubation period. *Acinetobacter* sp. produces organic acids while solubilizing phosphate present in a system. FVW contain phosphorus as orthophosphate, whose solubilization may be brought about by the aforesaid bacterial species. However, it has been observed that most white rot fungi, which are one of the most common microbial groups capable of degrading lignocellulosic biomass, prefer slightly acidic condition (pH 4.0 to 5.0) for their better growth and optimum activity^{36,37}. Studies have also revealed that the lowering of system pH, caused by a high enzyme activity, is largely dependent on the ligninolytic nature of the fungi. At low pH ranges, the activity of cellulase gets inhibited, whereas at high pH ranges most enzymes get dissolved thereby losing their activity³⁸. Thus the selection of two or more microbial species in a system aimed at accelerating the lignocellulosic biomass hydrolysis should be based on the nature of the waste complexity, the required degree of its treatment, and the extent to which the system pH remains. Since the pH of a culture medium plays a direct role in the secretion of enzymes (e.g. ligninolytic enzymes), which are required to breakdown the complex biomass, subsequent microbial metabolism and growth rate, it is of paramount significance that the culture medium/system pH be kept above a certain threshold.

E2. Co-Culture of microbes

The ability of lignocellulosic biomass, present in OFMSW, to undergo enzymatic hydrolysis is largely dependent on the synergistic action of two or more microbial culture. Since a single strain of bacterium or fungus is unable to produce every ligninolytic enzyme necessary to completely degrade lignocellulosic biomass, it may be a desirable strategy to co-culture two or more strains of bacteria or fungi in order to obtain an optimum level of enzymatic activity during the hydrolysis process. However, co-culturing of two or more bacterial or fungal strains is extremely challenging given the varying degree of

their genetic makeup, adaptive features, ecological niche and enzymatic components. Despite these challenges and the complexities to co-culture different species in a single medium, multiple attempts were made to grow different microbial species together with an aim to understand their interaction, enzyme secretions, and adaptation while trying to enhance the rate of lignocellulosic biomass hydrolysis³⁴. One of the crucial reasons in trying to test this strategy of co-culturing two or more microbes has been the ubiquitous nature of most microbial strains to degrade the recalcitrant bonding of biopolymers present in lignocellulosic components³⁹. Different bacterial-fungal combinations of pretreatments which have been thought of so far are as follows :

(i) **Bacterial co-culture** : Various studies aimed at co-culturing two or more bacterial species together with a view to accelerate the degradation of lignocellulosic biomass, present in OFMSW, and subsequent extraction of bio-fuel and value added products have been conducted so-far. Secretions of various cellulose-degrading enzymes (cellulases) by different strains of microbes, belonging to *Clostridium*, *Cellulomonas*, *Bacillus*, *Thermomonospora*, *Ruminococcus* and *Streptomyces* genus, have been the major underpinning for co-culturing two or more strains together^{40,41}. It was demonstrated in a study by Chandra *et al.*⁴² that the synergistic action of *Paenibacillus* sp., *Aneurinibacillus aneurinilyticus*, and *Bacillus* sp. bacterial strains was higher than the enzymatic potentials of the pure strains while hydrolyzing kraft lignin obtained from pulp-paper waste. In a separate study by Kato *et al.*⁴³, it was observed that the combined enzymatic action of *Clostridium straminisolvens* and three different strains of aerobic isolates had greater impact in degrading cellulose than that obtained by the individual microbes. Several other studies have revealed the effectiveness of combining different strains of rumen bacteria⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶ while hydrolyzing lignocellulosic biomass. Attempts have been made in these studies to understand the details of how the different ruminant bacteria co-

existed together, their network relationships and the mechanism of their synergistic enzymatic activity^{43,47}.

In order to achieve a stable co-culture, optimum media and growth requirements are imperative. Fine tuning of operational temperature, carbon source and atmosphere provide significant help towards equal growth of all the individual microbial strain present in a co-culture. Not only that, specific metabolic interactions such as, syntrophic relationships and alternative competitions for different substrate types, and other types of interactions (e.g. growth promoting or growth inhibiting interactions) also render stability to a co-culture⁴⁸. The reduction of exogenous elements, which causes metabolic imbalance for host cells, produced by a single bacterial strain is one of the major advantages of co-culture³⁹.

For instance, co-culturing of *Clostridium thermocellum*, which are capable of fermenting only hexose sugars, with other strains of anaerobic ther-

mophilic clostridia (such as *Thermoanaerobacterium saccharolyticum*, *Clostridium thermohydrosulfuricum*, *Thermoanaero bacterethanolicus* and *Thermoanaero biumbrockii*)^{49,50-55} capable of fermenting pentose sugars, greatly enhances the hydrolysis of cellulose and hemicellulose towards production of biofuels and ethanol. Fig. 2 represents a typical process flow-sheet for ethanol production from pretreated lignocellulose using *C. thermocellum* and *T. saccharolyticum* in co-culture. *Clostridium thermocellum* forms syntrophic associations with the thermophilic anaerobic strains and hydrolyzes cellulose to cellobiose and cellodextrins using cellulase enzymes, and hemicellulose to xylobiose, arabinoxylans and xylo-oligosaccharides using hemicellulase enzymes. Thereafter, the *C. thermocellum* utilizes the by-products of cellulose to produce ethanol, whereas the anaerobic clostridiums utilize the hydrolyzed by-products of hemicellulose to produce ethanol⁴⁸.

Fig. 2. Simplified process flow-sheet for ethanol production from pretreated lignocellulose using *C. thermocellum* and *T. saccharolyticum* in co-culture (Adopted from Ref. 48).

(ii) Fungal co-culture : One of the oldest and most widely practiced forms of multi-species microbial co-culture, targeted to enhance the degradation of lignocelluloses, is the fungal co-culture where two or more fungal species are co-cultured in a single media so that their synergistic co-existence may be utilized. Enzymatic hydrolysis using a single strain of fungi is mostly infeasible given the inability of most single fungal species to completely breakdown lignocellulosic biomass while in mono-culture⁵⁶. This is mainly due to the dearth of enzymes that are needed to achieve an optimum degree of lignocellulose hydrolysis. Co-culturing provides an opportunity for different types of fungi to treat the same lignocellulosic waste which would have been otherwise done by a single strain. This enhances product utilization besides minimizing the need for extracellular enzyme addition required for the waste degradation process. For instance, in case of cellulose degradation by fungi, three types of enzymatic components (EG, CBH and β -glucosidase) are needed in large amounts⁵⁷. However, none of the fungal strains are capable of se-

creting all those three enzymes simultaneously, let alone at large levels. *T. reesei*, for example, have been found to produce only EG and CBH in large quantities⁵⁸, whereas the secretion of β -glucosidase has been very poor. Co-culturing of *T. reesei* with *A. niger*⁵⁹, which produces enzymes rich in β -glucosidase component and limited EG components⁶⁰, would provide the best pathway towards maximizing enzymatic hydrolysis of the cellulose component of OFMSW via fungi. However, hydrolysis of OFMSW would also necessitate the removal of hemicelluloses, which in turn depends on the type of pre-treatment method adopted.

Alkaline pretreatment ensures the removal of a part of lignin thus allowing the degradation of hemicelluloses by hemicellulases. On the other hand, acid-catalyzed pretreatment hydrolyzes the hemicelluloses⁶¹ present in the waste thereby rendering the application of fungal co-culture to degrade hemicellulose to be techno-economically infeasible. Techno-economic feasibility via co-culturing of two or more fungal-strains to degrade lignocellulosic waste can only be achieved if the waste contains sufficient amount of celluloses and hemicelluloses. Despite the fact that some fungal-strains have shown to efficiently degrade hemicelluloses and celluloses independently in mono-cultures^{62,63}, it is understandably not advantageous to combine a pretreatment method (alkali or acid-catalyzed) with fungal mono-culture to degrade lignocellulosic waste. This is because the efficiency of the aforesaid strategy to hydrolyze lignocellulosic biomass is conspicuously lesser than the exclusive approach of hydrolyzing lignocelluloses using fungal co-culture as demonstrated by several studies in the recent past. It has also been observed that further conversion of cellulosic and hemicellulosic hydrolytic products in a single process can be achieved by co-culturing of two or more compatible fungal strains. Thus, unlike chemical pretreatment combined with mono-culture of microbes, only co-culturing provides an avenue to not only efficiently hydrolyze the lignocellulosic biomass but also the

conversion of the hydrolytic by-products into stable compounds. In fact, lignocellulosic biomass degradation in nature is underpinned by this same principle of microbial co-culture where multiple types of lignocellulolytic microbes co-exist to degrade lignocellulosic residues⁵⁷.

As such, widespread biological application of fungal co-culture, other than hydrolysis of solid organic waste, can also be found in the fields of antibiotic production, new types of enzyme production and various new types of fermented food⁶⁴. Examples of fungal strains co-cultured to hydrolyze celluloses and hemicelluloses include co-culturing of *T. reesei* D1-6 and *A. wentii* Pt 2804 in a mixed submerged culture, or that of *T. reesei* LM-UC4 and *A. phoenicis* QM329 using ammonia-treated bagasse⁶⁵. In both the aforesaid cases the major challenge had been the complexity in sustaining the growth of multiple microbes in the same culture medium⁶⁶. The co-culturing of *C. cellulolyticum* and *C. acetobutylicum* to enhance cellulose hydrolysis was another popular instance where co-culturing of fungal strains was proved to be a potentially consolidated bioprocessing approach aimed at enhancing the production of biofuels and biochemical from cellulosic biomass⁵⁶. At an optimal pH of 7.2, the co-culture of *C. cellulolyticum* with *C. acetobutylicum* showed a superior effect than the mono-culture of *C. cellulolyticum* in hydrolyzing cellulosic biomass⁶⁷. *C. acetobutylicum* complemented the cellulose degradation process, which was mainly carried out by *C. cellulolyticum*, by improving the cellulolytic activity of *C. cellulolyticum* via the exchange of metabolites, such as pyruvate. This exchange was extremely vital since it factored in the optimal growth of *C. cellulolyticum* and provided the much needed synergism even under complex co-culture conditions. In another study by Chi *et al.*⁶⁸ large amount of lignin degradation was reported in the co-culture of *C. subvermispora* and *Pleurotus ostreatus*.

(iii) Bacterial and fungal co-culture : Co-culturing of bacterial and fungal strains to promote en-

zymatic hydrolysis of lignocellulosic biomass is a relatively new approach where a dynamic consortium of microbes live together to communicate with each other and participate in interconnected network of food-web within the community. For example, the enzymatic activity of soil microbes present in non-sterile soil got enhanced when added to four strains of white rot fungi, (which included *Dichomitussqualens*, *Ganodermaapplanatum*, and two strains of *Pleurotus* sp.) which were cultured on milled straw. It was also observed that the laccase and manganese peroxidase production of *Pleurotus* sp. remained unaffected by the addition of the soil microbiota⁶⁹. The aforesaid instance of cellulose degradation holds similarity with the natural biodegradation of lignocellulose where different bacterial species in non-sterile soil synergistically interact with various fungal strains resulting in an enhanced enzymatic activity, which promotes the hydrolysis of the lignocellulosic biomass⁷⁰. The basic mechanism of the aforesaid lignocellulosic breakdown constitutes opening up of the recalcitrant bonding in the lignocellulose by fungi, followed by the hydrolysis of the cellulose and hemicellulose into soluble saccharides by the same, and the conversion of the hydrolyzed residues into valued end products by non-sterile soil bacteria. As such, the formations of popular value-added products have resulted from this novel approach of bacteria-fungi co-culture. Examples include production of isobutanol from the co-culture of *T. reesi* and *E. coli*⁷¹, and production of ethanol from *Z. mobilis* and *Pichia stipites*⁷². It was observed in a study by Golias *et al.*⁷³ that the production of ethanol was at a relatively faster rate in a co-culture of recombinant *Klebsiellaoxytoca* P2 with *Kluyveromycesmarxianus*, *Saccharomyces pastorianus* or *Z. mobilis* compared to that of a pure culture. This was accompanied by an increased cellulase activity. This higher enzymatic activity during the efficient breakdown of lignocellulose via bacterial and fungal interaction deems this co-culture strategy to be a better alternative to other techniques of involving enzymatic

hydrolysis⁷⁴.

E3. Microbial adaptation

One of the crucial factors which contribute to the rapid inter-species microbial adaptations in a co-culture is the need for different substrates⁴⁸. This absence of competition for substrates not only leads to the rapid degradation of the cellulosic biomass, but also facilitates the formation of value added end products. Despite that, the progress of inter-species microbial adaptations in a new environment is characterized by the population size of the species, their survival, spread and transmission in a specific ecological niche⁷⁵. The differences in the physiological properties of the population, their cellular structures, and the different ecological niches are telling adaptive-factors in a shared medium/environment⁷⁶. In addition, the better understanding of a species adaptive potential is served by studying its genetic make-up. The study of the genetic make-up provides important insights on the ability of the species to invade a new environment, and the adaptive advancements needed to survive in its existing ecological niche³⁴. Other essential studies needed for a better understanding of microbial adaptation include systematic laboratory experiments on molecular level and on aspects of ecology, understanding of the physiochemical parameters like pH, temperature, oxygen demand, and substrate requirement of individual microbes in advance so that optimization of these parameters can be done prior to the set-up of a co-culture⁷⁷. Even if all the aforesaid critical issues are well-studied and understood prior to the set-up of a co-culture, ensuring the prolonged survival and continued success of biologically active microbial consortia in a competitive and incompatible environment remain a major challenge.

E4. Temperature

The operational temperature during enzymatic hydrolysis is one of the discernible physical factors affecting microbial growth and their enzymatic activities. Also, the effects under a particular tempera-

ture regime vary greatly with the variation in microbial species³⁴. As such, the adaptability of different microbes varies with the variation in different operational temperature regimes. Based on their preference for a certain temperature regime, micro-organisms are classified into three distinct groups : psychrophilic bacteria (capable of growing in between -15° to 20°C), mesophilic bacteria (capable of growing in between 20° to 45°C) and thermophilic bacteria (capable of growing in between 41° to 122°C). Most bacterial and fungal species tend to thrive in a wide range of temperature spectrum, preferably in between 4° to 60°C . The mesophilic fungi and bacteria, which have their optimum temperature for growth in between 25° and 40°C , are commonly found and studied in the degradation of lignocellulosic biomass⁷⁸. It was found in one of the studies conducted by Wen *et al.*⁵⁹, involving the co-culture of *T. reesei* and *A. phoenicis*, that the operational temperature of 27°C and pH 5.5 provided the best condition for both the aforesaid fungal strains to thrive together and result in the enhanced production of cellulase and β -glucosidase. The fungal strains were co-cultured with an aim to degrade the cellulose fraction present in dairy manure waste. The selection of the optimum working temperature and pH was easier since the optimal working temperature and pH for both the fungal strains were almost similar (25.5°C and pH 5.76 for *T. reesei*; 28.2°C and pH 5.14 for *A. phoenicis*). The addition of micronutrients (KH_2PO_4 and CoCl_2) in the culture helped in the enhancement of the enzymatic activity. The pathogenic bacterial species, however, have an optimum growth temperature of 37°C , whereas most thermophiles prefer operational temperature to be above 45°C . On the other hand, white rot ascomycetes prefer an optimum temperature of 39°C for their growth, whereas basidiomycetes, similar to *T. reesei* and *A. phoenicis*, prefer the 25° – 30°C temperature range⁷⁹.

E5. Moisture content

The economic viability of a biological treatment process, such as that of enzymatic hydrolysis, can

only be realized if high substrate concentrations are managed. In order to do so, the treatment process has to be optimized. In case of enzymatic hydrolysis carried out at high concentrations of lignocellulosic biomass (solid state fermentation), the yield of sugar at the final stage may be adversely affected if the generation of inhibitory compounds, which arises from excessive dry matter decomposition, is not checked. In order to check the generation and accumulation of inhibitory compounds, without compromising the final sugar yield, the initial moisture content of the substrate has to be optimized. This is due to the fact that the establishment of the microbial growth, necessary to sustain the degradation of the lignocellulosic biomass, is largely dependent on the percentage of moisture present in the biomass/solid organic-waste. The initial moisture content of the biomass/substrate has been found to critically affect the growth and enzymatic activity of microbial species meant to degrade the biomass⁸⁰. Most bacterial and fungal strains prefer an optimum substrate moisture content of 40–70% for their optimum performance. For example, in a study conducted by Raimbault⁸¹ it was observed that the best output in terms of rice and coffee pulp degradation by *A. niger* was at a wide range of optimum moisture content in between 40 and 80%.

Earlier studies conducted by Reid³⁶, however, showed the need for a relatively higher optimum moisture content of 70–80% for ligninase activities of most white rot fungi, and subsequent lignin degradation. In a more recent study by Meehian *et al.*⁸², similar requirements of high optimum moisture content (85%) and low particle size were also reported in case of lignin and cellulose degradation with *Daedaleaflavida* MTCC 145. In another very recent study, Saha *et al.*⁸³ observed that the optimum moisture content level on white rot fungi *Phlebiabrevispora* NRRL-13108 to be around 84% during the enhanced hydrolysis of corn stover, and the production ethanol from it. In an earlier study by Shi *et al.*⁸⁴, it was observed that the degradation of

lignin, present in cotton stalk, by *Penicillium-chrysogenum* was enhanced when the optimum moisture content was around 75 to 80% than that at 65%. However, in a much recent study carried out by Fujian *et al.*⁸⁵, a lower solid liquid ratio was found to be more beneficial for the production of some crucial enzymes, such as manganese peroxidase and lignin peroxidase, required to degrade straw. It is evident that the optimum moisture content varies with the variation in the type of biomass and the microbes involved in the degradation process. A high percentage of moisture content would inevitably result in anaerobiosis and a very low percentage of it would cause inhibition of the microbial growth⁸⁶. Hence, optimizing the moisture content is extremely essential given that the microbes require free water for propagating³⁴.

E6. Biomass type

The nature of the biomass plays a significant role in the selection of the biological treatment type, and the type of microbial species to be employed, especially if enzymatic hydrolysis is selected. A compositional analysis of the biomass to be treated is thus essential since that gives a fair idea about the enzymes required to degrade the lignocellulosic biomass, and the type of microbes to be employed. The composition of the biomass greatly varies with species and variety, growth conditions and maturation. Lignocellulosic biomass is mostly composed of cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin, and other small amounts of organic and inorganic components like proteins, lipids and extractives. The wide availability of lignocellulosic biomass in the form of agricultural and forest residues, and energy crops is one of the major causes for the complex nature of the waste. This necessitates the application of various pretreatment techniques prior to the hydrolysis process so that waste degradation via microbes becomes techno-economically feasible and sustainable. However, pretreatment also poses the challenge of sugar loss. Thus structural complexity of the biomass and the loss of

sugar yield need a better understanding in order to optimize the enzymatic hydrolysis of lignocellulosic biomass for greater techno-economic viability.

(i) Structural complexity : The structural complexity of lignocellulosic biomass is due to crystalline nature of the cellulose, hemicellulose cover on cellulose and complex phenylpropanoid unit of lignin. These are mostly profound in plant cell walls resulting in increased recalcitrant biomass, which in turn are resistant to enzymatic degradation caused by microbes⁸⁷. The accumulation of I α and I β layers^{88,89}, which are forms of crystalline structure, on cellulose is a direct result of inter and intra-molecular hydrogen bonding in between the cellulosic chains^{90,91}. The lignin, besides having a very complex network of non-fermentable phenylpropanoid units, is highly insoluble in water due to the presence recalcitrant biopolymer. This recalcitrant nature together with the protective covering of non-fermentable phenylpropanoid units makes it difficult for the enzymes to bind onto lignin. On the other hand, the hemicellulose sheathing of the cellulose prevents the cellulase from reacting with the cellulose resulting in the inhibition of the lignocellulosic hydrolysis^{92,93}. Attempts have been made to pretreat lignocellulosic biomass, with an aim to remove the lignin content and reduce the cellulose crystallinity, so that the enzymatic action is maximized. However, the maximum yield of monomeric sugars from cellulose and hemicellulose fractions can only be achieved by the synergistic action of various efficient ligninolytic enzymes.

(ii) Polysaccharide loss : The loss of polysaccharide is a major concern during lignocellulosic treatment. The application of various pretreatments prior to enzymatic hydrolysis poses a great dilemma since an excess of the pretreatment would result in the loss of polysaccharides while a reduced degree of it would mean that the microbes have to do most of the cellulose deconstruction by themselves, which in turn would make the overall process of degradation very slow. As such, it has been observed from past stud-

ies that significant amounts of cellulose and hemicellulose fraction are lost as a result of biological pretreatment. This is attributed to the fact that some fungal species³⁴ while carrying out lignin degradation, sustain their growth by consuming monomeric sugars produced from cellulose and hemicellulose⁹⁴. The cellulolytic enzymes secreted by these strains of white-rot fungi digest some part of the produced sugar immediately after the enzymatic saccharification of cellulose, resulting in low yields of sugar. Thus optimization of the pretreatment technique along with the selection of the appropriate microbial strain, depending on the type of biomass to be treated, is extremely vital in order to minimize the loss of polysaccharide. In this regard, various techniques, such as genetic manipulation of microbial strains and alteration of the ligninolytic/cellulolytic enzymes, have come up to ensure least amount of sugar loss following lignocellulosic biomass degradation. However, further improvements are necessitated.

E7. Incubation period

The production of polysaccharides and ethanol from the delignification of complex lignocellulosic biomass can be significantly increased by optimizing the microbial incubation period. The incubation period varies with the type of lignocellulosic biomass chosen and the microbial strain employed for its degradation. Longer incubation time mostly stems from the low delignification rates and this more often than not is one of principal barriers in the large-scale commercialization of biological pretreatment of complex cellulosic waste. For instance, during the degradation of corn stalks by *Irpexlacteus*, a 37.5% loss of glucan and a 59.7% loss of xylan facilitated an overall 37.6% delignification after 42 h. Due to the significant degree of recalcitrant loss from corn stalks, brought about by xylan and glucan removal via enzymatic saccharification, there was significant loss of glucose. Thus a balance between the enzymatic saccharification rate and the polysaccharide-consumption rate during the aforesaid biological pretreatment

is essential in order for the process to be economically feasible⁹⁵. Zhong *et al.*⁹⁶ achieved a satisfactory yield of 64.3% cellulose after 60 days incubation period of corn stalks pretreatment with *I. lacteus*. The observed loss in the glucose yield was a result of such a long incubation period. The recalcitrant nature of lignocellulosic waste is thus one of the major hindrances in the efficient application of enzymatic pretreatment compared to several other physicochemical pretreatment methods. In order for enzymatic hydrolysis to be effective optimization of the incubation period has to be done.

E8. Aeration and substrate size

The production and activity of ligninolytic enzymes are greatly affected by the substrate particle size and the extent of aeration. Aeration helps in oxygenation, CO₂ removal, heat dissipation, humidity preservation and distribution of volatile compounds produced during microbial metabolism⁹⁷. The particle size and shape of the lignocellulosic biomass along with the capillary structure of the cellulosic fibers constitutes the external and internal surface area of the lignocellulosic biomass^{34,98}. Reduction of the substrate particle size ensures an increase in the external surface area thereby providing a scope for increased hydrolytic activity by different ligninolytic/cellulolytic enzymes. Larger substrate particle size makes it difficult for fungal enzymes to penetrate^{82,99}. Not only that, larger particle size also prevents diffusion of a substantial amount of oxygen during the event of aeration. This is attributed to the fact that, the larger the particle size the smaller the inter particle space and lesser the subsequent diffusion of air, resulting in a hindrance to the growth and metabolism of the participating microbes. The degradation of lignin is basically an oxidative process and lesser availability of oxygen would result in lesser ligninase activity of white rot fungi⁷⁹. In packed reactors, active aeration is a must to ensure uniform air diffusion, which is necessary for the consistent rate of lignin degradation. Delignification rates can,

however, be improved upon an increase in the aeration rate¹⁰⁰.

VI. Past experiences on enzymatic hydrolysis

So-far many researchers have explored the mechanisms underlying enzymatic hydrolysis and have come up with numerous strategies to enhance the degree of enzymatic hydrolysis. Most of these strategies, which mostly include physical, chemical, microbial and thermal pre-treatment techniques, are aimed at enhancing the enzymatic hydrolysis of lignocellulosic substrates present in the generated solid organic waste. Lignocellulosic substrates are the most difficult to degrade fraction of the generated solid organic waste.

One of the earlier pilot-scale implementations of enzymatic hydrolysis on solid organic waste was carried out by the team of Ropars *et al.*¹⁰². The process of converting the lignocellulosic biomass, present in agricultural wastes, into acetone-butanol (ABE) basically consisted of steam explosion pre-treatment of the raw material, cellulase production, enzymatic hydrolysis and acetone-butanol fermentation of hydrolysates. This was the very first pilot-scale operation where the influence of temperature, time, and addition of acids on both the performance of enzymatic hydrolysis and the fermentability into ABE of the hydrolysates obtained were observed. In addition, scale-up of the steam explosion pre-treatment of corncobs were done. It was observed that under optimal conditions, nearly quantitative hydrolysis yields were obtained by the use of moderate amounts of appropriate cellulase preparations.

In an attempt to improve the enzymatic hydrolysis of cellulose, the team of Zheng *et al.*¹⁰³ pre-treated cellulosic materials with supercritical carbon dioxide. The objective was to increase the cellulose reactivity so that the hydrolysis got improved. Various cellulosic materials, such as Avicel, recycled paper mix, sugarcane bagasse and repulped waste of recycled waste paper, were placed into a reactor, which was maintained under pressurized carbon dioxide at 35°C for a controlled period of time. The

cellulosic structures were disrupted by the explosive release of CO₂ pressure, resulting in the increase of the surface area of the cellulose. This in turn resulted in a greater degree of accessibility for cellulase necessary to carry out enzymatic hydrolysis. The penetration of CO₂, as a result of pressure increase, into the cellulose crystalline structures facilitated greater production of cellulosic materials. It was observed that this pre-treatment technique led to an increased glucose yield from cellulosic substances by as much as 50%. The production of ethanol ultimately got boosted as a result of this increased saccharification strategy.

Later on, in a separate study by Saha *et al.*¹⁰⁴ enzymatic saccharification of wheat straw waste to ethanol was carried out by dilute acid pre-treatment and enzymatic saccharification. For instance, long wheat straw has been looked upon as a low cost feedstock for ethanol production due to its high cellulose (48.57%) and hemicellulose (27.7%) content on dry solids (DS) basis. It was observed from the study conducted by Saha *et al.*¹⁰⁴ that 565 mg/g of monomeric sugar yield was possible from wheat straw (containing 7.83%, w/v, DS) by pretreating with dilute H₂SO₄ (0.75%, v/v). This was followed by enzymatic saccharification at 45°C and pH 5.0 for 72 h with the use of different enzymes such as, cellulase, β-glucosidase, xylanase and esterase. The effectiveness of the process was asserted from the fact that there was measurable quantity of furfural and hydroxymethyl furfural production, which is common by-product during ethanol production.

The team of Kristensen *et al.*¹⁰⁵ studied the feasibility of pre-treating monocot residues such as, cornstover and wheat straw, in producing bioethanol. These wastes are not fully exploited, for producing ethanol, since various factors such as, high enzyme loadings, makes economic utilizations difficult. It was observed from the present study that addition of non-ionic surfactants and polyethylene glycol during enzymatic hydrolysis of various lignocellulosic monocot residues resulted in the increase of cellulose con-

version by up to 70%. In addition, it was revealed from the investigations that various pre-treatment techniques such as acid and steam, prior to using surfactants, had a better impact on straw than pre-treatment via the use of ammonia and hydrogen peroxide.

In a recent study by Barakat *et al.*¹⁰⁶, enzymatic hydrolysis of lignocellulosic biomass was improved by application of an eco-friendly dry alkaline chemo-mechanical pre-treatment/technique. The pretreatment of lignocellulosic biomass, mostly constituting wheat-straw, was carried out using NH_3 , $\text{NaOHAH}_2\text{O}_2$, $\text{NH}_3\text{AH}_2\text{O}_2$ and NaOH at high materials concentration (5 kg/L) equivalent to a biomass/liquid ratio of 1 : 5 (dry chemo-mechanical), and at low materials concentration (0.2 kg/L) equivalent to a biomass/liquid ratio of 5 : 1 (dilute chemo-mechanical). Besides improving the enzymatic hydrolysis, the pre-treatment strategy proved to be significant in terms of better input energy savings, decreased environmental impact and non-production of waste and liquid by-products. The mechanical pre-treatment technique part includes, grinding and milling operations of the untreated and chemically treated wheat straw samples before enzymatic hydrolysis with commercial cellulases. The inclusion of NaOH and $\text{NaOHAH}_2\text{O}_2$, in the present study, in carrying out dry chemo-mechanical pre-treatments have been found to be more effective in decreasing the particle feed-stock size, increasing the particle surface area, and consuming of less energy when compared to the conventional mechanical pre-treatment techniques used earlier.

VII. Future scope

The benefits of enzymatic hydrolysis, in the field of AD of OFMSW, can be availed only if the critical issues in the said area are addressed properly. Several crucial variables, concerning enzymatic hydrolysis, affect the efficiency of the conversion process. These include biomass source, pre-treatment method adopted, source of enzyme, and enzyme mixture.

These are some of the most relevant components towards designing a process of lignocellulosic conversion. The optimization of the lignocellulosic conversion process can be easily devised if the aforesaid components are addressed. In addition, other strategies for optimizing the glucose yields by the use of fed-batch systems and additives, incorporating enzyme supplementation, various washing and detoxification steps, etc. are still very much needed to be explored both individually and in combination. Furthermore, new mechanisms that can make the conversion process more rapid are also need to be explored. Scope of designing of more robust reactors, which are capable of mixing biomass slurries so that there is minimal end-product inhibition, and no heat and mass transfer limitations have to be explored. In addition to all these, the cost of enzyme, biomass and any necessary special equipment as well as the optimum use of any potential by-products generated during the conversion process have to be addressed in the design stages. Also, the effect of enzymatic hydrolysis on various operational parameters such as, pH, organic loading rate, operating temperature and hydraulic retention time has to be standardized to make the most out of the enzymatic hydrolysis process and to ensure complete control over the overall AD process.

VIII. Conclusion

The present review clearly revealed the importance of applying enzymes in carrying out hydrolysis of the lignocellulosic fraction present in OFMSW. The various advantages of enzymatic hydrolysis like, improved overall process efficiency with faster rates, control over subsequent acidogenesis and methanogenesis phases, cost effectiveness, recovery of lignin and hemicellulose, etc. makes it a logical choice over conventional hydrolysis process. The impacts of enzymatic hydrolysis on various operational parameters like pH, organic loading rate, temperature are yet to be explored. Also, the pre-treatment technologies to overcome the recalcitrance of lignocellu-

loses can be improved to increase the enzyme accessibility of cellulose. There is also a vast array of enzyme sources that are yet to be utilized on a large scale basis. On this note, it can be concluded that even though enzyme mediated hydrolysis has immense potential the process has not been implemented on larger scales in developing countries due to the lack of sufficient knowledge. Once its cost effectiveness is established and the operational parameters are optimized suitably, it can be used commercially in developing countries.

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